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Research paper

A generalized machine learning approach for cost-effective monitoring of irrigation suitability: A demonstration case in El Fahs aquifer (Tunisia)

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HIGHLIGHTS

- A regressive machine learning approach was adopted to assess groundwater quality.
- Site-specific and generalized models were used to evaluate irrigation water quality.
- SVR and XgBoost identified as best-performing algorithms for IWQI prediction.
- Sodium is the most influential parameter in IWQI estimation in El Fahs aquifer.
- Dual focus on regional and global scales enhances versatility for IWQI assessment.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

This study develops and evaluates the performance of machine learning (ML) regression models, namely the Support Vector Regression (SVR), Random Forest (RF), k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XgBoost), for estimating the Irrigation Water Quality Index (IWQI) based on groundwater samples collected from El Fahs aquifer in Tunisia. The groundwater data are used as predictors for training and testing the machine learning models. Results indicate that sodium concentration has the most influence on the IWQI estimations for all ML models. The best-performing algorithms are found to be the SVR and XgBoost. Different datasets are also collected from existing studies, and merged to generate a single dataset that is used to develop generalized machine learning models. Despite regional variations, the generalized models performed adequately when tested against the unseen data, particularly the data collected from El Fahs case site. This work highlights the potential of using ML models, together with established metrics, as screening tools for predicting and classifying the irrigation suitability of groundwater based on available literature, even when metrics are not

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universally applicable. The findings of this study can be used by the water authorities in data scarce environments as cost-effective monitoring tools to assess water suitability for irrigation purposes.

1. Introduction

Water scarcity arises from the inability to satisfy the water demands based on the available water resources. Climatic changes and human-induced activities are the main drivers of this global issue (Leal Filho et al., 2022). These factors include spatio-temporal disparities in precipitation and evapotranspiration rates, land use changes due to population growth, economic development, and shifting consumption patterns. As a result, there is an urgent need to adapt environmentally sustainable technologies that aim at increasing water availability (Eliades et al., 2023; Martins et al., 2024; Panagiotou et al., 2024b; Panagiotou et al., 2023; Rene et al., 2019; Sallwey et al., 2019), mitigating the water quality deterioration (Güler et al., 2012; Konstantinou and Wang, 2023, 2024, Mastrocicco and Colombani, 2021) and optimizing the water allocation among the end users (Andreu et al., 1991; Rey et al., 2019).

This is a complex and resource-intensive task that requires a broad understanding of the interactions between the properties of the water systems and the underlying processes. It involves integrating multiple sources of information via various modelling tools (Güler et al., 2002, 2012; Panagiotou et al., 2022, Panagiotou et al., 2023, Panagiotou et al., 2024a) and employing various quality metrics to classify the water samples with respect to the target end-users (Chidiac et al., 2023; Meireles et al., 2010).

To address the challenges associated with assessing water quality and reducing the associated costs, machine learning (ML) techniques are often used to interpret relevant information and characterize the status of water systems. ML analysis provides an efficient way to identify underlying principles when these are largely unknown. Such analysis also enables the description of data in problems that are highly non-linear and complex.

Several studies have explored the application of machine learning techniques to characterize water status in terms of popular quality indices (Abdel-Fattah et al., 2021; Aldrees et al., 2024; Alfwzan et al., 2023; Chidiac et al., 2023; Haghiabi et al., 2018; Nasir et al., 2022; Shams et al., 2023; Zegaar et al., 2023). For example, Shams et al. (2023) developed several machine learning algorithms, such as random forests, support vector machine, gradient boosting and adaptive boosting to predict the water quality index (WQI) on a set of 1991 entries. Nasir et al. (2022) compared the ability of several classifiers to predict WQI and highlighted the ability of the CATBOOST algorithm in providing accurate predictions of this quality metric, allowing a comprehensive assessment of water quality. Recently, Zegaar et al. (2023) trained and evaluated the ability of several ML algorithms to predict the irrigation water quality index (IWQI) based on data collected from various locations in north-central Algeria. Mutual information, a feature-selection approach, was employed to identify the most influential factors for IWQI, found to be the total hardness, chloride and sulphate. These features were used as inputs to develop a simple, low-cost predictive model for the suitability of irrigation water. Despite the abundance of studies that report the successful use of ML models to identify connection patterns between water properties and processes, these studies focused on specific case sites that possess their own unique hydrogeological and hydrochemical characteristics.

The estimation, and consequently the classification, of the IWQI strongly depends on the statistical behaviour of the input features, especially on the minimum and maximum values which are required to determine the uppermost and lowermost borders of the classes. It is unclear whether ML techniques that are trained based on a single dataset collected from a particular region, can perform sufficiently well in assessing the quality status of other water systems.

To address this gap, this study focuses on a) the development of site-specific ML models based on groundwater samples collected from a plain aquifer located in Tunisia and b) merging hydrochemical data collected from five different groundwater systems into a single dataset to develop generalized models (GM) for properly characterizing the groundwater quality in a new 'unseen to the model' region. Another novelty of this study is the identification of the minimum number of parameters required to assess reasonably well the quality of irrigation water, applicable to both site-specific and generalized datasets.

Additional contributions of this study are i) the assessment of the directionality of the input variables with respect to the IWQI and the identification of threshold values beyond which irrigation quality degrades substantially (with the use of partial dependence plots), ii) the use of regressive instead of classification ML models to categorize groundwater quality and iii) the partitioning of the dataset into various combinations of training/splitting subsets to reduce model bias and increase confidence about the performance of the ML models, and to maximise data utilisation in the presence of relatively small datasets.

2. Methodology

An overview of the methodology adopted in this study is shown in Fig. 1 (a). Groundwater samples are collected from shallow monitoring wells in El Fahs plain aquifer (NE of Tunisia). This aquifer represents a typically stressed hydrosystem located in a semi-arid region where water availability and quality are crucial for irrigation purposes. The collected samples are used as input variables (features) in the ML models. Prior to building the machine learning models, an exploratory analysis was conducted to characterize the statistical patterns of these variables (e.g., extreme outliers, skewness, correlations across input parameters, etc.). Particularly, histograms were constructed for each input variable, whereas correlation analysis was performed using Pearson and Spearman coefficients to detect highly correlated variables. For each ML algorithm, various models were developed by randomly splitting the dataset into multiple training and testing subsets. The accuracy of the compiled models was assessed based on widely used error indicators to determine the most appropriate ML model. An interpretation of the best-performing model was conducted with the use of feature importance and partial dependence plots (PDPs), which were also used to identify the most influential factors to the IWQI predictions. The best-performing algorithms were then used to develop a ML model based on hydrochemical characteristics of other groundwater systems as documented in the existing literature, termed the 'generalized' model. The performance of the generalized ML model was then tested against the El Fahs aquifer data.

2.1. Groundwater data collection from El Fahs aquifer and calculation of IWQI

Groundwater samples were collected from 35 shallow monitoring wells (Fig. 1), at depths ranging from 20 to 25 m below the ground surface, within El Fahs aquifer during a single campaign in April 2016. The concentrations of total hardness (TH), electric conductivity (EC), along with the water temperature (T), were measured on-site with portable instruments, whereas laboratory analyses were conducted to measure the concentrations of eight major ions (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , HCO_3^-) and total dissolved solids (TDS). Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR) was calculated via the following equation:

$$SAR = \frac{[Na^+]_{meq}}{\sqrt{0.5 \times ([Ca^{2+}]_{meq} + [Mg^{2+}]_{meq})}} \quad (1)$$

where $[.]_{meq}$ denotes that the ion concentration is measured in milliequivalents per litre (meq/l).

The computation of the IWQI requires the classification score of the water samples, represented by q_i , based on the concentration values for five quality parameters (Table 1).

According to Table 1, q_i values below 35 exist only if the highest value of a quality parameter exceeds the concentration values corresponding to $q_i = 35$. Similarly, q_i values greater than 85 can occur only if the lowest value of a parameter is smaller than the value

corresponding to $q_i = 85$. As a result, four quality classes are constructed based on the threshold limits of q_i : [0-35], [35-60], [60-85] and [85-100]. The actual value of q_i value is estimated by applying a linear interpolation between the upper and lower limits of the quality class α , selected via Table 1:

$$q_i = \left\{ q_{max} - \Delta q \frac{(x_i - x_{min})}{\Delta x} \right\}_\alpha, i = 1, \dots, n_s \quad (2)$$

where q_{max} is the maximum value that q_i can have within quality class α , n_s is the total number of sampling locations, x_i is the concentration value of the considered parameter, x_{min} is the minimum concentration value of a parameter within that class, $\Delta q = q_{max} - q_{min}$ is the difference between the lower and upper limits of the selected class, and $\Delta x = x_{max} - x_{min}$ is

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 1. (a) Flow chart of the current methodology and sampling distribution within the Tunisian case site, along with (b) the geographical location and (c) the geological and hydrogeological settings of El Fahs plain.

Table 1

Determination of quality classes based on proposed threshold values of the irrigation parameters, along with the associated weights as reported in Meireles et al. (2010).

q_i	EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	SAR (meq/L) ^{1/2}	Na^+ (meq/L)	Cl^- (meq/L)	HCO_3^- (meq/L)
100	200	SAR_{\min}	2	Cl_{\min}	1
85	750	3	3	4	1.5
60	1500	6	6	7	4.5
35	3000	12	9	10	8.5
0	max (EC)	max (SAR)	max (Na^+)	max (Cl^-)	max (HCO_3^-)
Parameter weights rowhead					
w_i	0.211	0.204	0.202	0.194	0.189

the difference between the minimum and maximum concentration values of the considered parameter within class α . The above process is conducted for all quality parameters.

Subsequently, the IWQI was calculated at each sampling location by multiplying the q_i values for the five parameters with their corresponding weights w_i , listed in Table 1 and via the following equation:

$$\text{IWQI}_i = \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^5 w_k \times q_k \right\}_i \quad i = 1, \dots, n_s. \quad (3)$$

2.2. Models' development

The collected groundwater data are used to calculate the IWQI (target/output variable), and as input data for the development of the machine learning (ML) models for predicting the IWQI at each sampling location. Eleven parameters are selected as input variables, namely the concentrations of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} and HCO_3^- , the total dissolved solids (TDS), the concentrations of total hardness (TH), electric conductivity (EC) and the water temperature (T). Table S.1 (supplementary material) presents various ML algorithms commonly used for classification and regression, along with their major advantages and disadvantages (Dineva and Atanasova, 2020; Flach, 2012; Jha, 2021). Most of these algorithms have been used for groundwater-related applications. In this study, four ML algorithms are considered for regression in accordance with Konstantinou and Stoianov (2020), particularly:

1. Random Forests (RF): This algorithm utilizes an ensemble learning method to create multiple decision trees. For regression tasks, each decision tree predicts a numerical value for the target variable, whereas the final prediction is found by averaging the predictions obtained from all trees (Breiman, 2001; Hastie et al., 2009).
2. eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XgBoost): Similar to RF, this algorithm utilizes ensembles of decision trees within a gradient boosting framework, enhancing predictive accuracy through the iterative combination of weak learners (Friedman, 2001).
3. Support Vector Regression (SVR): This algorithm minimizes the dissimilarity (error) between predicted and actual values so that it is bounded within a pre-specified margin via regularization terms, whereas kernel functions are used to identify linear connections among input-output variables into higher-dimensional variable spaces (Kecman, 2005).
4. k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN): For regression tasks, this algorithm provides predictions of a target variable by averaging the values of k-neighbouring datapoints, whereas Euclidean distance is used as the dissimilarity metric within the feature space.

The hyperparameters for each machine learning algorithm underwent tuning via cross-validation on a training set, comprising 70% of the entire dataset. The remaining 30% constituted a hold-out sample or test set, which was used to evaluate the trained models. Prior to this split, the data were shuffled to remove any inherent ordering or biases that could

potentially interfere with patterns or sequences in the data.

2.3. Performance indicators

The performance of the models was assessed based on the root mean square error (RMSE) and the mean absolute error (MAE) between the predicted and actual values (given by Equations 4 and 5).

In particular, RMSE quantifies the deviation of the predicted from the actual values by squaring their differences, averaging these squared differences, and then taking the square root of the average:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{n}}, \quad (4)$$

and MAE equals the average value of the absolute error between the predicted and actual values:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |\hat{y}_i - y_i|}{n}, \quad (5)$$

where \hat{y}_i denotes the predicted values, y_i denotes the actual values of the output variable and n denotes the total number of observations.

The coefficient of determination (R-squared value) was also used in this study to quantify how well the model's predictions explain the variation in the actual values. This is relevant in cases where data points are not expected to fall precisely on the 1:1 line, as most regression models are designed to capture trends and relationships rather than make predictions identical to the actual values. Although the R-squared value may not be the most appropriate metric for the specific needs of this work, it is included to complement the other two metrics because it is commonly used in other studies and is easy to understand, thereby aiming to address a broader audience of practitioners.

2.4. Models' interpretation

The feature importance process aims at identifying the most influential variables of a ML model. Particularly,

1. For regressive RF, Gini impurity is used to determine the best split across individual trees within the ensemble. The increase in node purity is calculated by the decrease in the total sum of squared errors when a variable is selected for splitting.
2. For XgBoost algorithm, the most significant features are identified by the 'gain' of a feature which measures the improvement in accuracy brought by a feature to the branches it is on. The term 'gain' (similar to the Gini index) is a measure of how much the selected feature contributes to minimizing the overall mean squared error (MSE) of the model.
3. Regarding SVR, the feature importance is assessed based on the absolute mean of the coefficients of the support vectors. Features associated with higher absolute mean coefficients compared to others are considered more influential to the SVR's decision function.
4. For kNN, it is obtained by measuring the deterioration of predictive accuracy due to the omission of a particular variable.

Additionally, the sensitivity of the output variable to the variations of each feature separately is evaluated via partial dependence plots (PDPs). These plots illustrate the marginal effect of an input variable on the predicted outcome while holding the other input parameters constant, set equal to their average value.

3. Study area

The El Fahs Aquifer is situated in the central valley of the Miliane watershed within the Zaghouna governorate, approximately 60 km south of Tunis (Fig. 1(b-c)). Encompassing an area of 619 km², the

aquifer is part of the El Fahs plain. It is geographically delineated by various geomorphological features, particularly: to the north by the Beni Kleb and Rouissat mountains and the Korzia wetland (Sebkha), to the west by the Bouarada plain and Mansour Mountain, to the south by the El Kef Lazreg and Bent Saidane mountains, and to the east by the El Fahs hills.

The plain is characterized by a semi-arid climate with an average annual precipitation of 325 mm, and an annual evapotranspiration rate of around 1400 mm (Institut National de la Météorologie, 2022), indicating a significant hydrological deficit in the area. The landscape is defined by a well-established hydrological system, primarily composed of the Miliane wadi and its tributaries, including wadi Kebir, wadi Jarabaa, and wadi Boudhebbane. The El Fahs aquifer is crucial to the region's water supply and socio-economic growth, serving as an essential water source for agriculture. It supports the irrigation of fertile plains in the surrounding areas, enabling the cultivation of crops such as cereals, vegetables, and fruits, enhancing the region's agricultural productivity, and contributing to food security.

From the geological viewpoint, the study area is characterized by E-W and NW-SE grabens controlled by a series of NE-SW and E-W faults, along with the presence of Triassic outcrops (Hachani et al., 2020; Panagiotou et al., 2024a). The geological formations range from the Triassic to the Quaternary. Triassic formations, which consist of gypsum, limestone, and dolomite, are exposed northwest of El Fahs city and are marked by irregular stratigraphy due to salt diapirs. Jurassic formations, comprising limestone and marls, are located in the southwestern part of the plain in Bent Saidane Mountain. Cretaceous outcrops, primarily surrounding the plain, are made up of limestone, marly limestone, and marls. In the southwestern part of the plain near Mansour Mountain, marly and calcareous deposits from the Paleocene and Eocene periods are present. Oligocene outcrops, formed by limestone and alternating beds of marls and sandstone, are mainly found in the west and south of the plain. Miocene and Pliocene formations, composed mostly of continental sediments such as clays, sandstone, and conglomerate, are exposed in the north and southeastern parts of the plain. The central part of the plain is predominantly made up of Quaternary deposits, which include red silt, limestone crusts, and alluvia along the wadis.

Groundwater resources are hosted in a shallow aquifer mainly composed of porous Mio-Plio-Quaternary deposits of alluvium, sand, silts, and clays. It is an unconfined aquifer system where the groundwater flow is strongly influenced by topographical characteristics. Piezometric records revealed that the main groundwater flow directions are in one hand from the uplands of mountains Rouissat and Beni Kleb in the North and Mansour in the South towards Sebkha Korzia, and on the other hand from El Fahs hills in the East, Bent Saidane Mountain in the Southeast and Kef Lazreg in the South towards the center of Wadi Miliane plain.

In a very recent study, Panagiotou et al., 2024a combined various graphical and clustering tools to group the groundwater samples (the same samples used in the current study) into three distinct classes based on their hydrochemical composition. The first class, primarily located in the central part of the plain near a dense hydrological network, exhibits the lowest salinity due to the recharge effect of the Kebir Wadi. The second class, characterized by Na-Ca-Cl facies, is predominantly found in the central and southeastern parts of the aquifer. The high electrical conductivity (EC) values in this class have been attributed to the irrigation return-flow phenomenon. The third class, mainly consisting of Ca-Mg-HCO₃ facies, is mostly found in the southeastern part of the aquifer, associated with calcareous and evaporite outcrops. The primary hydrochemical process governing this part of the aquifer is carbonate dissolution, which enriches the groundwater, particularly with bicarbonates and calcium.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Exploratory analysis

Eleven parameters were monitored in the area under examination and were used as input variables, namely the concentrations of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} and HCO_3^- , the total dissolved solids, the concentrations of total hardness, electric conductivity and the water temperature. The concentrations of other indicators have been excluded from this analysis because they were measured at a much smaller number of wells, thereby limiting their statistical characterization and the robustness of the results of the ML models. The reason behind the limited sampling of additional parameters stems from the high cost and the time-consuming process that makes the sampling and analysis of nitrates and various heavy metals a challenging task in these environments in Tunisia. Subsequently, only in-situ parameters (e.g., EC, T, pH) and major ions have been analyzed, representing a limitation of this study.

Fig. 2 shows the frequency distribution of the groundwater data, revealing that the majority of these parameters exhibit roughly normal behaviour. Strong asymmetries towards small values (positive skewness) and discontinuous distributions in the presence of outliers are observed for Na^+ , K^+ and Cl^- .

Table 2 shows the correlation coefficients among the measured parameters. The upper triangle of the table displays the Pearson correlation values, used to quantify the strength of the linear relationship between pairs of variables, and the lower triangle of the table displays the Spearman rank correlation values, used to quantify the strength of the monotonic relationship between pairs of variables. In the presence of high Pearson correlation coefficient (>0.85) between two variables, one of them was removed to resolve multicollinearity and maintain the structural integrity of the model. As expected, the TDS is found to be highly correlated to EC (0.92), therefore the former variable is not considered as a potential predictor (feature) of the ML algorithm. Sodium, EC/TDS and chlorine are also found to be significantly correlated with the IWQI (less than -0.5). A non-trivial discrepancy between the Pearson (-0.86) and Spearman (-0.80) coefficients is evident for sodium, revealing a stronger monotonic than linear relationship with IWQI in the presence of weak non-linearity. Similar behaviours are observed for variables that exhibit weaker correlations with IWQI, such as sulphates, magnesium and bicarbonates.

4.2. The performance of the ML models

Due to the small size of the dataset, six different splitting modes of the dataset into training and testing subsets are considered, resulting in the generation of six ML models for each algorithm (24 models in total). Consequently, an ensemble of six models per ML algorithm is created, providing a more comprehensive view of how these models perform across various scenarios and data partitions. This task was conducted to maximise data utility, reduce variability (by averaging performance metrics), and provide a better assessment of the findings and robustness of the models.

The comparison between the actual and the predicted values based on the various testing sets, together with the RMSE and MAE for each ML algorithm, is shown in Fig. 3 and Table 3, respectively. It is observed that the kNN models exhibit the worst performance among all ML algorithms, with RMSE values ranging between 3.8 and 6.2 (MAE ranging from 2.7 to 5.3 and R-squared values from 0.56 to 0.786) across the various testing sets. The RF algorithm performs reasonably well in terms of RMSE, ranging from 1.9 to 5.5. The best-performing algorithms are found to be the SVR and XgBoost algorithms, with RMSE values ranging from 1.0 to 2.5 and from 2.0 to 4.2, respectively. The MAE values vary from 0.8 to 1.6 for the SVR algorithm, and from 1.3 to 2.6 for the XgBoost algorithm, whereas the R-squared values vary from 0.91 to 0.98

Figure 2. Histograms of the physico-chemical parameters. The vertical axis represents the frequency of occurrence within an interval.

Table 2

Pearson (upper triangle) and Spearman (lower triangle) correlation coefficients for all pairs of variables.

	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Na ⁺	K ⁺	HCO ₃ ⁻	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	TDS	TH	T	EC	IWQI
Ca ²⁺ rowhead	1	-0.19	0.02	-0.01	-0.03	0.41	-0.03	0.31	0.42	-0.03	0.23	-0.07
Mg ²⁺ rowhead	-0.15	1	-0.16	-0.21	0.13	0.21	0.35	0.31	0.24	-0.14	0.23	0.05
Na ⁺ rowhead	-0.19	0.14	1	0.45	-0.16	0.18	-0.06	0.07	0.09	-0.10	0.09	-0.80
K ⁺ rowhead	-0.32	0.03	0.42	1	-0.29	-0.07	-0.01	-0.02	0.02	-0.02	-0.08	-0.23
HCO ₃ ⁻ rowhead	-0.06	0.18	0.05	-0.21	1	0.08	0.54	0.23	-0.02	-0.03	0.31	-0.27
Cl ⁻ rowhead	0.27	0.53	0.20	-0.09	0.23	1	0.16	0.68	0.48	0.29	0.78	-0.54
SO ₄ ²⁻ rowhead	-0.04	0.40	0.07	-0.26	0.62	0.54	1	0.59	0.12	0.13	0.59	-0.31
TDS rowhead	0.22	0.46	0.13	-0.25	0.31	0.68	0.70	1	0.58	0.32	0.92	-0.49
TH rowhead	0.46	0.41	0.10	-0.08	0.07	0.56	0.25	0.56	1	0.06	0.48	-0.26
T rowhead	-0.07	-0.08	-0.03	-0.27	-0.02	0.13	0.17	0.24	0.10	1	0.37	-0.08
EC rowhead	0.09	0.45	0.16	-0.23	0.43	0.79	0.80	0.87	0.43	0.23	1	-0.58
IWQI rowhead	0.02	-0.21	-0.86	-0.22	-0.33	-0.52	-0.36	-0.44	-0.25	-0.02	-0.54	1

for the SVR algorithm, and from 0.65 to 0.87 for the XgBoost algorithm. Therefore, the most reliable models among all cases are found to be the SVR and XgBoost. As shown in Fig. 3, both algorithms fail to predict accurately one or two points for each testing set, and in the case of XgBoost, this point is further away from the 1:1 line compared to the case of the SVR algorithm.

Fig. 3 also shows the relative importance of the input variables for the four ML algorithms. Generally, the results are consistent with the correlation analysis provided in the previous subsection, revealing that sodium is by far the most influential parameter for all ML algorithms, whereas the selection of the least influential feature varies among the different algorithms (temperature for RF and SVR, potassium for kNN and TH for XgBoost).

Chloride and bicarbonate appear twice as the second most important features, suggesting that they should also be included as features in the machine learning models. Another important parameter is found to be the electrical conductivity, especially for RF and SVR, although this variable appears to have the second highest correlation value among all input variables with respect to IWQI (sodium is found to have the highest value).

The consistency among all ML algorithms in terms of the selection of the most important features (i.e., Na⁺, Cl⁻, HCO₃⁻ and EC) regardless of the choice of splitting modes, signifies that these indicators could be used for the prediction and assessment of groundwater quality. These parameters are inherently linked to the IWQI because of their direct impact on groundwater chemical processes. Specifically, EC serves as a

Figure 3. Predicted Vs. actual IWQI values and feature importance: the top figures show the predicted and actual IWQI values using (a) the kNN, (b) the RF, (c) the SVR, (d) the XgBoost algorithms for the various testing sets. Each symbol denotes a splitting mode of the dataset (six in total). The bottom figures are bar plots displaying the relative importance of all features in estimating the IWQI. Each colour refers to a specific pair of training/testing subsets (six in total).

Table 3

The RMSE, MAE and R-squared values for the testing sets of the six splitting modes of the dataset.

Model/Testing set	1	2	3	4	5	6
kNN	5.149	3.951	4.803	4.073	3.797	6.261
	4.096	2.919	3.565	3.245	2.686	5.346
	0.560	0.755	0.670	0.479	0.741	0.786
RF	4.254	3.541	4.918	1.450	3.722	5.865
	3.122	2.273	3.328	1.314	2.620	5.035
	0.828	0.662	0.657	0.892	0.836	0.903
SVR	1.804	1.073	2.189	1.255	2.189	2.536
	1.237	0.812	1.461	0.961	1.253	1.612
	0.958	0.978	0.924	0.925	0.909	0.925
XgBoost	2.899	2.001	4.244	2.005	2.925	3.779
	2.263	1.309	2.718	1.513	1.944	2.631
	0.811	0.858	0.650	0.738	0.843	0.886

* The first number refers to the RMSE value, the second refers to the MAE values, and the third refers to the R-squared value.

strong indicator of the total dissolved salts in water, which affects salinity levels and in turn influences soil structure and crop health. High concentrations of Na^+ and Cl^- can cause ion toxicity in plants and deteriorate soil properties, whereas HCO_3^- is vital for maintaining the alkalinity and buffering capacity of water, thus affecting pH levels and the solubility of other ions. As such, these parameters are essential for evaluating water's suitability for irrigation since they directly affect soil chemistry, crop growth, and long-term soil health, making them crucial indicators in IWQI evaluations.

The variations of the selected features among the different ML algorithms can be attributed to their distinct underlying principles. Complex models like Random Forest (RF) and XgBoost are able to capture intricate data patterns involving non-linearities, and identify complex relationships among variables due to the various feature combinations that occur in decision rules. Support Vector Regression (SVR) and k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) aim at finding high-dimensional hyperplanes or clusters, in a high-dimensional space.

Opting for diverse machine learning models contributes to a better understanding and confidence in interpreting the examined problem. Specifically, the four most important parameters identified from all ML algorithms (Na^+ , Cl^- , HCO_3^- and EC) can be used to reduce the dimensionality of the problem and allow for more economic evaluation of groundwater quality. This is shown in Table 4, where different models were built for the two best-performing algorithms, each by adding one feature at a time, starting from sodium concentration. The error values are decreased each time a new feature is incorporated, with the largest error reduction associated with the addition of EC. This observation highlights the high influence of sodium and EC on the IWQI predictions, indicating that the usage of only these two variables for the development of ML models can provide accurate predictions of the quality index. Consequently, simpler and less money-consuming evaluations of this index can be proposed.

To further assess the influence and 'directionality' of the input variables, partial dependence plots (PDPs) are used based on the best-performing algorithms, particularly the SVR and XgBoost. The PDPs

Table 4

The RMSE, MAE and R-squared values for models built based on different features.

Features	SVR (RMSE/MAE/R-squared)	XgBoost (RMSE/MAE/R-squared)
Na^+	4.259/3.530/0.625	7.277/5.906/0.265
Na^+ + EC	2.847/1.951/0.820	3.274/2.380/0.829
Na^+ + EC + Cl^-	2.605/1.869/0.843	3.212/2.363/0.825
Na^+ + EC + Cl^- + HCO_3^-	2.191/1.375/0.941	3.074/2.213/0.888

*The first number represents the RMSE value, the second is the MAE and the third is the R-squared value.

offer additional information compared to feature importance as they provide a way to evaluate the sensitivity of a model to variations in a single feature while keeping fixed the values of the remaining inputs of the training subset, set equal to their mean values. Fig. 4 shows the PDPs for the variables of the highest importance, namely, the Na^+ , Cl^- , HCO_3^- and EC. Smaller variations are observed for the less important parameters and therefore, these are not shown.

The relationships between input variables and IWQI are represented by curves in the SVR model, exhibiting an almost linear profile. The highest reductions of IWQI occurred while increasing EC and sodium concentrations. In the case of XgBoost model, which is able to sufficiently capture the non-linearities and the more complex interactions, the IWQI reduces dramatically for EC values larger than 3000 $\mu S/cm$, and completely degrades for values larger than 6000 $\mu S/cm$. The largest decreasing trend of IWQI is associated with increasing values of sodium. A rapid decrease of IWQI is observed with increasing sodium concentrations up to 1000 mg/l, beyond which the groundwater quality completely degrades. A decreasing trend of IWQI is observed with the increase of chloride concentration until 3500 mg/L, after which sharp reductions are observed. Regarding bicarbonates, minor variations of IWQI values are observed for values less than 250 mg/L, followed by sudden reductions for almost the entire remaining range.

Fig. 4(b-c) depicts the PDPs of the two major pairs of features ($[Na^+, EC]$ and $[Na^+, Cl^-]$), showing a deterioration of water quality (decrease of IWQI) with increasing values of these pairs. However, this appears to take place earlier in the case of $[Na^+, EC]$ compared to $[Na^+, Cl^-]$ pair, mainly because lower concentrations of sodium are associated with larger reductions of IWQI for a given value of EC, compared to chlorine.

4.3. Comparison of the findings with the data from the literature

As shown in the previous section, the sodium concentration is found to have significantly higher impact on IWQI than the variables appearing in the original expression (Equation (2)) and the model input parameters, regardless of the choice of ML algorithm. The remaining parameters (including SAR which is expressed in terms of sodium, calcium and magnesium) have a much smaller influence on the quality index, despite the fact that they have almost equal weights on the definition of IWQI (Table 1). Furthermore, the irrigation water quality index, a data-driven metric, is defined by considering the maximum and minimum values of each parameter within each specific region as shown in Equation (2). This approach results in a so-called 'site-specific normalization.'

To address the above limitation, this subsection discusses the development of generalized ML models by merging hydrochemical datasets collected from other groundwater systems, resulting in a single dataset with a much larger size than the dataset collected from El Fahs. The extended dataset is used to train generalized models (GM), which is tested against the hydrochemical dataset obtained from El Fahs aquifer, which is not included in the training process of the GM.

Groundwater data are collected from five other studies (Abbasnia et al., 2018; Al-Kubaisi et al., 2022; Al-Saffawi et al., 2020; Batarseh et al., 2021; Hegazi et al., 2018), also located in arid and semi-arid environments, and merged into a single dataset (see Table S.2 in supplementary material). Correlations among the different variables and the output variable (IWQI) are shown in Fig. 5. As expected, all studies suggest a high positive correlation between total dissolved solids and electrical conductivity, ranging from 0.97 to 1. Sodium and chloride exhibit moderate to high correlation values (ranging between 0.746 and 0.959). High correlations between pH and major ions (mainly HCO_3^- and SO_4^{2-}) are observed in the study by Al-Saffawi et al. (2020), and Kubaisi et al. Al-Kubaisi et al., (2022) (mainly Na^+ and Cl^-), whereas almost no correlations between pH and other variables are observed in the study by Hegazi et al. (2018). This discrepancy might be attributed to the fact

Figure 4. (a) Partial dependence plots for the major input variables. The y-axis represents the IWQI values. (b–c) Partial dependence plots for two pairs of input variables.

Figure 5. Pearson correlation matrix of the different variables based on the data reported in (a) Abbasnia et al. (Abbasnia et al., 2018), (b) Al-Saffawi et al. (Al-Saffawi et al., 2020), (c) Batarseh et al. (Batarseh et al., 2021), (d) Hegazi et al. (Hegazi et al., 2018) and (e) Kubaisi et al. (Al-Kubaisi et al., 2022).

that the latter study considers a larger dataset than the former one, which results in bias mitigation.

All studies exhibit high correlations among the majority of the considered ions and the IWQI, although some of these studies are ‘biased’ towards a single variable, similar to the El Fahs site. For example, the study conducted by Abbasnia et al. (2018) shows a stronger correlation between sodium and IWQI compared to the other variables, whereas EC exhibits the strongest correlations with IWQI based on the data reported in Al-Saffawi et al. (2020) and Hegazi et al. (2018).

The extended dataset comprises 244 entries (rows) and five input variables (columns), namely EC, SAR, Na^+ , Cl^- , HCO_3^- , which are selected as they are the common variables across the different studies

and found to have significant influence on IWQI based on the findings of the site-specific models. As stated before, EC is a strong indicator of the total dissolved salts in water, which impacts salinity levels, whereas SAR reflects the potential for sodium to accumulate in soil, which can affect soil permeability and structure. Elevated levels of Na^+ and Cl^- can lead to ion toxicity in plants, whereas HCO_3^- plays a crucial role in the alkalinity and buffering capacity of water, influencing pH levels and the solubility of other ions. Two ‘generalized’ ML models were built, each one using SVR and XgBoost algorithms, because these algorithms exhibited superior performance than all the other models based on the Tunisian dataset, as discussed in the previous section. The selected ML algorithms were trained using the entire extended dataset (244 entries), and

subsequently tested against the El Fahs groundwater data.

The RMSE values of the training and testing sets for the SVR model fluctuate between 5.898 and 4.565 respectively, whereas the RMSE values of the training and testing sets for the XgBoost model vary between 3.352 and 4.051. The comparison between the actual IWQI values (calculated based on Equation (2)) and the predicted values is depicted in Fig. 6(a–d). Both generalized models achieve reasonable agreement with the observed values, however, the performance of XgBoost is found to be higher than SVR. This result differs from the analogous comparison between these two algorithms for the site-specific models, already discussed in the previous section, partly due to the fact that the extended dataset possesses higher complexity, and hence non-linear interactions between the input parameters. As such, the XgBoost algorithm performs better in the extended dataset, whereas the SVR algorithm performed better in the smaller dataset that includes the data collected from El Fahs aquifer.

A wide range of IWQI values is present in the extended dataset that covers all quality classes (see Table 1), attributed to the wide range of the input variables. This observation highlights an important aspect of the generalized model as machine learning models are limited in predicting values outside the range of variables encountered in the training set (characteristic of data-driven models). Therefore, covering all groundwater quality classes in the input dataset provides the GM with a competitive advantage compared to the site-specific models. GM provides reasonable fits as most of the values are concentrated around the 1:1 line, whereas only two data points significantly deviate from this line.

Consequently, a good agreement is achieved between model predictions and the actual IWQI values provided by the regional dataset,

even though this dataset is not considered in the training process. The IWQI values of the testing set (i.e., El Fahs dataset) exhibit a narrower range, and the generalized model's ability to effectively capture groundwater quality of the El Fahs aquifer hinges on the importance of the variable that expresses the sodium ions. This importance is more pronounced in the model developed solely from the data collected from El Fahs aquifer (site-specific model), whereas sodium demonstrates a high correlation with IWQI based on findings from literature-examined studies (Yildiz and Karakuş, 2020). Specifically, sodium emerges as the most influential parameter in El Fahs dataset, whereas electrical conductivity (EC) takes precedence (28% for SVR and 53% for XGBoost) in the generalized dataset. The sodium and SAR are the next most influential factors, with percentages around 22% for both factors in the case of SVR, and 26%, 11% for the XGBoost model, respectively. Despite these differences, the models adeptly capture the underlying trends since in both cases sodium concentration falls in the most important variables, hence, showcasing that the patterns identified in the regional dataset also exist in the generalized dataset.

Consequently, the IWQI metric, combined with the use of the generated two-featured machine learning models, is shown to be a robust tool for predicting responses in new regions previously “unseen” by the trained model. This is attributed to the capacity of machine learning models to capture non-linearities, a task that simple multiple regression models struggle to achieve.

As shown in Table 5, different SVR and XgBoost models were developed with various combinations of input features to achieve feature reduction. In all cases, the XgBoost algorithm demonstrates better handling of larger datasets when compared to the SVR algorithm, as its performance is found to be always superior compared to the SVR

Figure 6. Comparison between predicted and actual IWQI values for (a–b) the training (merged information collected from literature) and (c–d) testing (data collected from El Fahs case site) datasets.

Table 5

The RMSE, MAE and R-squared values for models consisting of different feature combinations.

Features	SVR		XgBoost	
	Training (RMSE/MAE/ R-squared)	Testing (RMSE/MAE/ R-squared)	Training (RMSE/MAE/ R-squared)	Testing (RMSE/MAE/ R-squared)
All	5.898/3.630/ 0.908	4.565/3.129/ 0.671	3.352/1.945/ 0.971	4.051/3.265/ 0.684
Na ⁺ + EC	7.362/4.952/ 0.861	7.698/5.391/ 0.064	5.708/4.127/ 0.913	6.241/4.968/ 0.239
EC + SAR	6.782/4.616/ 0.883	7.315/6.088/ 0.293	6.312/4.619/ 0.895	5.392/4.276/ 0.779
EC + SAR+ Na ⁺	6.733/4.361/ 0.884	9.156/6.305/ 0.399	5.378/3.840/ 0.923	5.482/4.513/ 0.424

*The first number refers the RMSE value, the second refers to the MAE, and the third refers the R-squared value.

models.

Regarding SVR model, the best performance for a reduced feature dataset was achieved when (Na⁺, EC) parameters were used, whereas in the case of XgBoost this was achieved with the use of (EC, SAR). The performance of both two-featured generalized ML models is similar to that of the ML models developed using all input variables. Therefore, in situations where various parameter measurements are lacking, these simplified models can be employed for estimating IWQI.

The spatial distribution of the actual IWQI (Equation (3)) in El Fahs aquifer is shown in Fig. 7 (a). According to the classification theme (Equation (2)), the sampling locations are grouped into two quality classes. Particularly, samples with an IWQI value less than 35 are categorized under the ‘severe restriction use’ class, which means that groundwater cannot be used to irrigate soils under normal conditions, restricted only to high salt tolerant plants. These samples represent 17% of the total considered samples, mainly belonging to class 2 of the Piper diagram produced by Panagiotou et al. (2024a), characterized by high salinity due to the dissolution of the evaporate rocks and the phenomenon of irrigation return-flow. The remaining samples have IWQI value ranging from 35 to 60, hence are categorized under the ‘high to moderate restriction use’ class, meaning that these samples are suitable to irrigate moderate to high salt tolerance plants. Overall, groundwater can be utilized in soils with moderate to high permeability, considering moderate soil leaching processes and a frequent irrigation schedule, particularly when the irrigation water has an EC greater than 2000 µS/cm and a SAR exceeding 7 (Batarseh et al., 2021).

Fig. 7 (b) illustrates the spatial distribution of the predicted IWQI values via the best-performing generalized ML model (XGBoost), being able to correctly capture the quality classes at the large majority of the sampling locations. The relative error between the actual and predicted values of the quality index is also presented to quantify their discrepancies via the following formula:

$$e = 100\% \frac{(IWQI_{ac} - IWQI_{pr})}{IWQI_{ac}}, \quad (6)$$

where subscripts (\cdot)_{ac} and (\cdot)_{pr} denote the actual and predicted values respectively.

Compared to the actual case, three samples (i.e., F5, F26, and F29) were shifted from ‘severe restriction’ to ‘high to moderate restriction’, whereas three others (i.e., F7, F20, and F34) were reclassified in the reverse order. Consequently, the generalized model provides satisfactory predictions for the IWQI, despite not being trained based on the specific dataset, and despite the fact that in the training period the model has not ‘seen’ similar underlying physical phenomena.

5. Conclusion

A regressive ML modelling approach is adopted for groundwater quality assessment, departing from conventional classification methods. In particular, this study introduces and evaluates site-specific machine learning (ML) models based on a hydrochemical dataset collected from El Fahs aquifer (Tunisia), and generalized ML models based on consolidated and integrated hydrochemical data collected from various groundwater systems as reported in the literature. First, the irrigation suitability of El Fahs aquifer in Tunisia is assessed via the use of four different ML algorithms, particularly RF, SVR, XgBoost and kNN. Six different training/testing subsets have been generated via random splitting of the dataset due to its relatively small size, aiming to maximise data utilisation and overcome limitations associated with the use of small datasets in relevant studies. The most influential parameters are identified for the selected algorithms, revealing that sodium plays the most important role, followed by EC, Cl⁻ and HCO₃⁻, for the estimation and classification of the IWQI. An almost monotonic decrease of this index is observed with increase of sodium concentration until it reaches 1000 mg/l, beyond which a sharp decrease of the index is observed.

Another limitation that this study attempts to overcome is the fact that typically only in-situ parameters are measured, resulting in a limited number of variables and poor hydrochemical characterization. Therefore, hydrochemical information from five other groundwater systems is collected from literature and merged to a single dataset, which is used as input to train the best performing ML algorithms, namely, the SVR and XgBoost algorithms. The groundwater data of El Fahs aquifer are used as a testing set for the generalized model, resulting in accurate predictions of IWQI, showing that the generalized model is able to provide accurate predictions of this quality index in ‘unseen’ regions.

This dual focus on both site-specific and generalized modelling enhances the versatility and applicability of the developed models, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of groundwater quality dynamics. The minimum number of parameters, particularly two, that are essential for assessing water irrigation quality are identified for both site-specific and generalized datasets. This work demonstrates that machine learning models in conjunction with well-established relevant metrics can be used as a screening tool to classify water resources in terms of their quality based on the available literature.

This study opens new avenues for assessing water suitability for irrigation purposes in poorly monitored hydrosystems. It could constitute an important asset for the national and regional water authorities in Tunisia (or other regions with similar climate conditions) to support their decision of using available water for irrigation as an important step towards the sustainable water resources management in the region.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Constantinos F. Panagiotou: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Charalampos Konstantinou:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anis Chekirbane:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Spatial distribution of the IWQI (a) actual values in El Fahs aquifer (Equation (3)) and (b) predictions with XGBoost algorithm (displayed percentages at every sampling location denotes the relative error e).

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsd.2024.101324>.

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